

Job Commitment in Oyo and Ogun States Civil Service: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

The study empirically examined Job Commitment in the Nigerian Civil Service. Job commitment is someone's attitude towards work. It is a unifying factor (mind-set) that guides work behaviour. This study adopted a descriptive survey design to determine the level of job commitment among junior civil servants in Offices of Head of Service, Ministries of Finance, Education, Science and Technology in Oyo and Ogun states. The target population was estimated to be 342. The study utilised the purposive sampling and a structured questionnaire was administered to 79 junior civil servants. Data collected were analysed using frequency and percentage counts for the primary data. For the secondary analysis, responses were summed; mean and standard deviation scores were used. The results revealed that these junior civil servants exhibited low affective, continuance and normative job commitment because of their dispositions and experiences at work. They have little affection for their duties and poor work attitudes. The study concluded that low job commitment is one of the problems facing the civil service system in Nigeria. It is therefore, advised, that the government rekindle the system by boosting the morale and promoting the human capital development of civil servants by conducting regular training programmes, prompt payment of salaries and adequate incentives.

Keywords: Job commitment, Oyo state, Ogun state, civil service

Introduction

Job commitment is a human relations concept that involves human energy generation and mental activation. The psychological condition is what connects a person to an organisation. It revolves around putting new concepts into practice and, where required, compromising on initiatives. This can manifest as a commitment and involvement, a sense of duty, or an understanding of the gravity of quitting the organisation. One of an organisation's greatest advantages is its dedicated workforce which has a noteworthy impact on the general profitability and efficiency of the organisation (Igella, 2014). A high degree of job commitment fosters organisational advantages like cost and efficiency improvements through active participation. Increases in job performance, job satisfaction, sales, total return to shareholders, employee turnover, dissatisfaction, and desire to leave, as well as lower absenteeism and intention to look for other employment, all influence job commitment.

Job commitment is an important organisational construct which has been used interchangeably with organisational commitment. Omilani (2023) citing Kester, Olajide and Ogidan (2010) see job commitment as the employee's attitude and concern which his/her loyalty to the organisation. Meyer, Vandenberghe, and Becker (2004) referred to organisational commitment is the connection that workers have with their organisations. Generally, dedicated workers relate to the workplaces, feel like they belong, and understand the objectives. Employee attachment and loyalty to the company, as well as their desire to be a part of it, are ways that this is expressed. These workers have the added benefit of being more proactive in providing support, more driven at work, and comparatively productive.

Josje (2016) submitted that there are various ways that employee commitment can manifest itself in terms of development, direction, and context. Confusion and disagreement may also arise around the degree to which commitment affects conduct. This is further explained below:

- i. Connection to a goal: A specific level of commitment is demonstrated by the capacity to be bound to a goal; the drive to pursue a goal regardless of its source; and the capacity to believe in a goal and desire to attain it constantly.
- ii. Connection to an organisation: An individual is bound to the organisation through a psychological state. Therefore, employees are less likely to leave an organisation when they are more loyal to it.
- iii. Connection to the job: This is the tendency that someone will continue at a place of work and will feel psychologically bound to it. It is believed that job satisfaction/ fulfillment enhances job connection because a person who is not fulfilled in his job cannot be committed to the job (Rusbult & Farrell, 1983).
- iv. Job commitment is someone's attitude towards work. It is a unifying factor (mind-set) that guides work behaviour.

Aydin, Sarieran and Uysal (2011) stated that organisational commitment is the quality of excellence, and the process where an employee is accountable to the norms and objectives of the organisation. Simply, organisational commitment can be simplified as loyalty. This is the degree at which an employee is loyal to the organisation, the zeal to put in effort in representing the organisation. It is an indication of objectives and values that align with the organisation and a desire to keep members. Organisational commitment is the willingness to sustain organisational membership, aligning with the objectives and organisational successes. It describes employees' loyalty and the maximum input into such organisation. Incentives play a vital in environments with high levels of job commitment. It is an important factor in the development of civil servants' level of job commitment and has been identified as personal characteristics of civil servants as well (Starnes & Trubon, 2006). Job commitment is highly associated with incentives. Job commitment will be higher when civil servants gain what is needed most through incentives. The more incentives received by civil servants, the more committed the civil servants are to the jobs.

Civil service is an executive arm of government that formulates and implements the programs and policies efficiently and effectively to enhance national development. The government's reputation is safeguarded by this executive branch as an apparatus, which carries out policies effectively without jeopardising position and stability. The effectiveness of government machinery depends largely on the civil service (Nebo & Nnamani, 2015). Government goals, strategies, and programs are translated into public goods and services by the civil service for the benefit of the populace. The civil service is intended to be the main force behind the country's social and economic advancement. This contributes to the government's core duty of providing citizens with efficient and timely services.

Oyelere, Opute & Akinsowon (2015) state that the civil service revolves around people to achieve the desired results. The civil service is organised into four classes: junior cadre, executive, professional, and administrative. These classes consist of workers who oversee and control every facet of the economy. Civil servants are key players in the task of governance, and the degree of socio-economic progress of the country is linked to their job commitment (Omilani, 2023). The civil servants in Nigeria determine whether the civil service succeeds or fails. It is commitment that gets the work done and this is a paramount to the success of the civil service.

Job commitment is the duty a civil servant has to the civil service's mission and objectives. This is in the relative strength of civil servants' identification with, involvement and loyalty within the civil service system. Various scholars affirmed that most civil servants in Nigeria defy emotional attachment, identification and involvement. Also, organisational perception and attitudes of civil servants have eroded the need for commitment in the civil service. Over the years, practices such as bureaucracy, ethnicity, absenteeism, red tapism, lack of professional development policies by government through which successive governments were unable to institutionalise a proper legal framework contributes low job commitment among civil servants. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (2014) reported that "Nigerian civil servants' lack of job commitment has contributed to the nation's declining economic development trends". This corroborates the submission of Agbanero (2023),

"The civil service has been undergoing gradual and systematic reforms and restructuring since May 29, 1999 after decades of military rules. However, the civil service is still considered stagnant and inefficient; the attempts made in the past by panels have little effect on the promotion of sustainable human development in Nigeria".

According to the aforementioned, job commitment in the Nigerian civil service is a key element for the growth and development of this nation. Based on the researcher's perception of the trend in the Nigerian civil service, this study was conducted to fill the gap produced by lack of job commitment among junior civil servants in the Offices of Head of Service, Ministries of Finance, Education, Science and Technology in Oyo and Ogun states.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. ascertain the level of job commitment among junior civil servants in Oyo and Ogun states.
2. access the impact of monetary incentives on job commitment of junior civil servants in Oyo and Ogun states
3. determine the effect of non-monetary incentives on job commitment of junior civil servants in Oyo and Ogun states

Research Questions

1. What is the level of job commitment among junior civil servants?
2. What is the impact of monetary incentives on job commitment?
3. What is the effect of non-monetary incentives on job commitment?

Methodology

This study utilised a descriptive survey design to determine the level of job commitment among junior civil servants in Oyo and Ogun states. Both states have long history of the civil service system which can be traced to old western region in Nigeria. The population consists of all junior civil servants in Oyo and Ogun states. The target population was estimated to be 342 from the staff book. The study utilised the convenience sampling method to choose 79 junior civil servants: Oyo state was 47, while Ogun State was 32 as a result of the screening conducted using a scale for the junior civil servants by the researcher; those that scored below the criteria norm of 50% of an average score level of 100% was regarded as having low job commitment and with previous records of low commitment at work and met the inclusion criteria.

The study utilised a structured questionnaire consisting of demographic characteristics (age, sex, marital status, grade, and years of service), The civil service job commitment questionnaire (CSJCQ) was modified and adapted from organisational commitment questionnaire by Meyer and Allen (1997) and Mowday, Steers and Porter (1979). It used the five likert rating scale with responses. The multiple choice questions to cover affective commitment 1-6, continuance commitment 7-16, normative commitment 17-19, monetary incentives 1-3 and non-monetary incentives 1-2. The participants responded to each question on a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly Disagree=1, Disagree=2, Undecided=3, Agree=4, Strongly Agree=5)

Before the commencement of data collection for the study, approval for conduct of study was obtained from the Department of Adult Education, University of Ibadan, Offices of the Head of Service, Oyo and Ogun states. Also, informed consent was sought and obtained from civil servants, who were assured of the confidentiality of the information provided before participating in the study. The data collected were analysed using the SPSS. For descriptive variables, frequency and percentage counts were used to present the data. For the secondary analysis, responses were summed; mean and standard deviation scores were used.

Results

Table 1 Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

Sex	Frequency (N=79)	Percentage (100%)
Male	42	53
Female	37	47
Age group	Frequency (N=79)	Percentage (100%)
20-24	6	7.6
25-29	10	12.7
30-34	19	24.1
35-39	17	21.5
40-44	14	17.7
45-49	7	8.9
50 years and above	6	7.6
Marital Status	Frequency (N=79)	Percentage (100%)
Married	60	76
Single	19	24
Grade Level	Frequency (N=79)	Percentage (100%)
1	1	1.3
2	13	16.5
3	1	1.3
4	19	24.1
5	9	11.4
6	36	45.6
Years of service	Frequency (N=79)	Percentage (100%)
0-5	8	10.1
6-10	44	55.7

11-15	10	12.7
16-20	5	6.3
21-25	6	7.6
26-30	6	7.6

Table 1 shows that 53 percent were males, while their females were 47 percent. This shows that the civil servants who exhibited low job commitment included both sexes. About 8% of the respondents were within 20-24 years, 12.7% were within 25-29 years, 24.1% were within 30-34 years, 21.5% were within 35-39 years, 17.7% were within 40-44 years, 8.9% were within 45-49 years and 7.6% were 50 years and above. This shows that junior civil servants could exhibit low job commitment regardless of age.

24% of the respondents were single and 75.9% were married. This shows that the respondents cut across both married and single employees. 13% of the respondents were Grade 1 staff, 16.5% of the respondents were Grade 2 staff, 1.3% of the respondents were Grade 3, 24.1% of the respondents were in Grade 4, 11.4% of the respondents were Grade 5 and 45.6% of the respondents were Grade 6. This shows that the participants for the study include junior employees ranging from grade 1 to 6.

10% of the respondents had 5 or below years of work experience, 55.7% respondents had between 6-10 years of service, 12.7% had between 11-15 years, 6.3% had between 16-20 years, 7.6% had between 21-25 years, and 7.6% had 26-30 years of work experience.

Table 2: Dimensions of Job showing job commitment level of the junior civil servants

s/n	Job commitment	SD	D	U	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1. Affective Commitment								
1	Will you be happy to spend the rest of your career with the civil service?	18 22.8%	22 27.8%	12 15.2%	15 19.0%	12 15.2%	3.00	1.330
2	Do you enjoy discussing the civil service system with people outside?	34 43.0%	9 11.4%	11 13.9%	14 17.7%	11 13.9%	3.24	1.332
3	Do you feel as if the civil service problems are your own?	28 35.4%	18 22.8%	12 15.2%	9 11.4%	12 15.2%	3.20	1.275
4	Do you feel like you are part of the civil service system?	38 48.1%	8 10.1%	10 12.7%	5 6.3%	18 22.8%	3.71	1.123
5	Do you feel emotionally attached to the civil service system	38 48.1%	11 13.9%	11 13.9%	6 7.6%	13 16.5%	3.52	1.153
6	Do you feel a sense of belonging to the civil service system?	28 35.4%	23 29.1%	12 15.2%	4 5.1%	12 15.2%	3.68	1.193
2.Continuanace commitment								
7	Are you afraid of what might happen if you quit your job without another one in waiting?	7 8.9%	17 21.5%	16 20.3%	16 20.3%	23 29.1%	3.39	1.344
8	Will it be very hard to leave civil service if you want to?	8 10.1%	21 26.6%	15 19.0%	21 26.6%	14 17.7%	2.85	1.282
9	Will things be too much disrupted in your life if you decide to leave the civil service?	8 10.1%	26 32.9%	19 24.1%	16 20.3%	10 12.7%	2.92	1.207
10	Will it be too costly for you to leave the civil service now?	9 11.4%	19 24.1%	17 21.5%	22 27.8%	12 15.2%	3.11	1.261
11	Is your staying with the civil service a matter of necessity?	10 12.7%	20 25.3%	14 17.7%	24 30.4%	11 13.9%	3.08	1.279
12	Do you have few options to consider leaving the civil service?	15 19.0%	21 26.6%	15 19.0%	21 26.6%	7 8.9%	2.80	1.275
13	Is lack of available alternative one of reasons for staying in the civil service?	19 24.1%	9 11.4%	19 24.1%	14 17.7%	18 22.8%	2.89	1.281
14	Is leaving the civil service a considerable sacrifice for another	13 16.5%	11 13.9%	11 13.9%	24 30.4%	20 25.3%	2.58	1.429

	organisation which does not give same benefits?							
15	Do you think moving from one organisation to another is the best?	10 12.7%	10 12.7%	16 20.3%	21 26.6%	22 27.8%	2.57	1.346
16	Do you think moving from one organisation to another seem unethical?	12 15.2%	26 32.9%	15 19.0%	8 10.1%	18 22.8%	2.92	1.403
3. Normative Commitment								
17	If you get an offer for a better job, will you leave the civil service?	8 10.1%	19 24.1%	10 12.7%	17 21.5%	25 31.6%	3.41	1.410
18	Is loyalty an important reason for you to stay in the civil service system?	30 38.0%	20 25.3%	8 10.1%	8 10.1%	13 16.5%	3.52	1.309
19	Were you trained to believe in the value of remaining loyal to the civil service system?	31 39.2%	13 16.5%	11 13.9%	16 20.3%	8 10.1%	3.03	1.339

Affective commitment: Table 2 above shows items 1-6 affirmed low affective commitment. Approximately, 34% respondents agreed when asked if they were happy spending the rest of their career with the civil service, 50.6% respondents disagreed and 15.2% respondents were undecided. 31.6% respondents agreed to discussing the civil service system with people outside, 54.4% respondents disagreed and 13.9% respondents were undecided. 26.6% respondents agreed sharing a sense of belonging with the civil service and seeing its problem as theirs.

Continuance commitment: Results from items 7-16, buttressed that the junior civil servants have low continuance commitment. 58.2% respondents disagreed and 15.2% respondents were undecided. 29.1% respondents agreed to be part of the civil service system, 58.2% respondents disagreed and 12.7% respondents were undecided. 29.1% respondents agreed that they are part of the civil service system, 58.2% respondents disagreed and 10(12.7%) respondents were undecided. 14.1% respondents agreed to being emotionally attached to the system, 52% respondents disagreed and 3.9% respondents were undecided. 20.3% respondents agreed having a sense of belonging to the civil service, 55.5% respondents disagreed and 15.2% respondents were undecided. 49.4% respondents agreed being afraid and quitting the job for another, 30.4% respondents disagreed and 20.3% were undecided. 44.3% respondents agreed that it would be hard to leave the civil service if they wanted to do, 36.7% respondents disagreed and 19% respondents were undecided. 33% respondents agreed that things will not be disrupted if they decide to leave the civil service, 43% respondents disagreed and 24.1% respondents were undecided 43% respondents agreed that it would costly to leave the civil service, 35.5% respondents disagreed and 21.5% respondents were undecided. 44.3% respondents agreed that staying in the civil service is a matter of necessity as much as they desire, 38% respondents disagreed and 17.7% were undecided. 35.5% respondents agreed having few options considered in leaving the civil service, 45.6% respondents disagreed and 19% respondents were undecided. 40.5% respondents agreed to the lack of available alternative as a reason for staying in the civil service, 35.5% respondents disagreed and 24.1% were undecided. 55.7% respondents

agreed to leaving the civil service as a sacrifice for another organisation, 30.4% respondents disagreed and 13.9% respondents were undecided. 55.4% respondents agreed that moving from one organisation to another is the best, 35.4% respondents disagreed and 20.3% respondents were undecided. 32.9% respondents agreed that moving from one organisation to another seem unethical.

Normative commitment: Results from items 17-19, indicated that junior civil servants have low normative commitment to their jobs. Approximately, 48% respondents disagreed and 19% were undecided. 53.1% respondents agreed to leaving the civil service for a better job, 34.2% respondents disagreed and 12.7% respondents were undecided. 26.6% respondents agreed that loyalty is an important reason for staying in the civil service, 63.3% respondents disagreed and 10.1% were undecided. 30.4% respondents agreed to being trained to believe in the value of loyalty to the civil service system, 55.7% respondents disagreed and 13.9% respondents were undecided.

Table 3: Showing the impact of monetary incentives on job commitment

Monetary Incentives								
1	Is your salary, bonus, leave allowance, and other benefits paid as and when due?	24 30.4%	21 26.6%	7 8.9%	16 30.4%	11 13.9%	3.29	1.503
2	Is health insurance and pension fund available and accessible to you?	18 22.8%	24 30.4%	10 12.7%	19 24.1%	8 10.1%	3.29	1.554
3	Do you benefit from increment in salary regularly?	26 32.9%	17 21.5%	8 10.1%	14 17.7%	14 17.7%	3.08	1.448

Monetary incentives

The findings on items 1-3 indicated low monetary incentives among junior civil servants. About 44.3% respondents agreed that salary, bonus, leave allowance and other benefits are paid as at when due, 57% respondents disagreed and 8.9% respondents were undecided. 34.2% respondents agreed to the availability and accessibility to health insurance and pension, 53.2 % respondents disagreed and 12.7% respondents were undecided. 35.4% respondents agreed that they benefit from salary increment regularly, 54.4% respondents disagreed and 10.1% respondents were undecided.

Table 4: Showing the impact of non- monetary incentives on job commitment

Non-monetary incentives								
1	Do you receive letters of appreciation and awards often?	20 25.3%	22 27.8%	6 7.6%	16 20.3%	15 19.0%	3.20	1.497
2	Do you go on training and development programmes regularly?	26 32.9%	21 26.6%	14 17.7%	7 8.9%	11 13.9%	3.54	1.269

Non- monetary incentives

The results on items 1-2 deduced that junior civil servants have low access to non-monetary incentives. 39% percent of the respondents agreed to receiving letters of appreciation and awards often, 53% respondents disagreed and 8% were undecided. 22.8% respondents agreed to attending training and development programmes regularly, 59.5% respondents disagreed and 17.7% respondents were undecided. The findings indicated that junior civil servants are not often appreciated on the job, are not given regular awards and do not go on training and development programmes.

Discussion of findings

These junior civil servants exhibited low affective job commitment. This could be in support of various assertions by scholars that junior civil servants have low job commitment based on attitude to work, personal experiences, peer / family pressures and economic status of the country. According to Bajumon, 2015, personality traits could also be responsible for low continuance commitment exhibited among the junior civil servants. This does not align with Aydin, Sarier & Uyusal (2011) who stated that employees must belief in the norms of the organisation and must have maximum input at work. They stay on the job because there is no better alternative and can leave anytime there are better offers. Most junior civil servants stay on the job for survival and having a means of income no matter how little compared to being jobless. Low normative commitment indicated that the junior civil servants have poor dispositions to their jobs and experiences at work. They have a little affection for their duties and poor work attitudes. Some of these junior civil servants work because of the social norms of leaving home and having somewhere to go. Other colleagues believed that they could only perform better, if incentive strategies were injected and executed in the system. This supports Meyer and Allen (1997) employees will always be on the job because of obedience, formality, cautiousness and the societal norm of people who work are responsible.

The monetary incentives available to junior civil servants such as salary, bonus, leave allowance, health insurance and pension scheme are not commensurate to the job roles and assumed to be poor with the present economic situation of the country. Kimutai & Sakata (2015) submitted that a good pay system will help every employee to perform well and increase work productivity. Also, according to Mamdani & Mimhaj (2016), a good reward system with high incentives will improve and increase the work quality, thereby giving the employees and organisation mutual advantages.

Non –monetary incentives are inadequately received by these junior civil servants, who are not often appreciated on the job, are not given regular awards and do not go on training and development programmes. There is the need to appreciate employees through gifts, training programmes, vacations, free meals among others as stated by McShane & Ghinow (2010). Letters of appreciation, office celebrations, coffee and lunch break, job rotation and inter departmental transfer could be helpful.

The understanding of junior civil servants on job commitment was poor. The prior understanding by these civil servants was that the civil service system was mainly controlled by the government and that individual's job schedule had little impact on the system. Several of these junior civil servants do not put much effort into the system, they are not proud to talk about the civil service system to friends. In addition, many of them do not have aligned personal values with that of the system. This agrees with the opinion of Salami (2014) who believes that poor organisational behaviour is a factor responsible for poor performance and failure of agencies in the public sector which is undoubtedly unproductive, stagnant and inefficient. Results from Kester (2008) showed a significant relationship between ethnic politics and civil servants commitment in government organisations, where, working attitude is based on factors like religious beliefs, urbanisation, intermarriages, familiarities and friendship. In fact, these

junior civil servants believed that the civil service does not really bring out the best in them and it is not the best organisations to work for. Sanya (2016) observed that timely, consistent appearance in the workplace, teamwork, involvement at work, excitement for the job, sense of duty and internal observations were low in civil service establishments. However, the findings of this study attest to the need for convenient techniques for the training of junior civil servants on job commitment. It was deduced that there was the need for participants to become knowledgeable about job schedules and dedication in improving and boosting the job commitment at work.

Conclusion

This study makes it clear that these junior civil servants exhibited low job commitment and this is one of the problems facing the civil service system in Nigeria. It is therefore, advised, that the government rekindle the system by boosting the morale and promoting the human capital development of civil servants conducting regular training programs, prompt payment of salaries and adequate incentives. Excellent service deliveries among these civil servants should be well recognized through awards. A vibrant and health civil service is the key to good governance and national development.

Recommendations

There is the need for these junior civil servants to become knowledgeable about their job schedules, dedication and ensure all hands are on deck in improving/ boosting the job commitment at work. This study attests to the need for these employees to embrace convenient techniques for trainings on job commitment. The government should address the problems affecting the civil service system such as the working attitude, low morale/motivation, inadequate incentives, sabotage, and interpersonal conflicts among others. Also, the government should integrate behavioural interventions, motivational incentives such as training, prompt payment of salaries, recognition, awards to promote the culture of commitment within the civil service system.

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